

PROBLEMS OF MODERN EDUCATION

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Education plays an important role in society. But, as in any other area, it has a number of problems that need to be addressed as soon as possible. This article discusses the actual problems of modern education.

Keys words: education, education management, problems of modern education.

We all know that education has played and continues to play a huge role in our lives. After all, it is the future of our nation, our country. And most people, maybe not all, but most of them are interested in getting an education, namely in getting a quality education. Recently, people are increasingly asking the question: “Do children get quality education now?” At school, and at home, they constantly say that if you study well, you will get a worthy and highly paid profession. But is it really so? It must be admitted that the quality of education in our time is not the best. In this case, several problems can be identified. The first problem is the assessment of students individually and according to the same criteria. Is it correct? After all, someone has a better developed memory and logical thinking, while someone has a creative one. But this does not mean that a person is stupid or mentally retarded. The 21st century is the age of information technology. Every day there is more and more new information. And remembering everything at once is almost impossible. Now even teachers cannot be sure of their answers, because knowledge quickly becomes outdated and loses its relevance.

The second problem is the low level of communication between the stages of

education. This problem especially concerns school graduates and first-year students. For admission to universities in our time, USE scores play a huge role. But to successfully pass the exams, the modern school does not provide enough knowledge, so many parents have to hire tutors for their children for additional classes. And the services of a tutor are quite an expensive pleasure and not everyone can afford it. This gives the impression that the possibilities of the school and the requirements of the state do not correspond to each other. The third problem is the availability of education, but the lack of work. A person receives a diploma, but it turns out that very often there is no work in his profession. What is it connected with? This is due to the fact that now in many areas of activity requires work experience. Many employers do not want to hire people without experience. And where can a newly graduated university graduate get this experience? Unclear. Earlier, when our grandparents and parents were still educated, they were confident in their future. In their time, finding a job by profession was easy and simple. And now it is not education that plays a big role in this matter, but the availability of money and connections.

The next problem, perhaps, concerns not only education, but also many industries. This is insufficient funding. That is why the education system lacks a large number of personnel. To keep up with the times, you need to constantly update equipment and technology, introduce new technologies. Not all educational institutions have enough funds for this. The fifth problem is a lack of understanding of what profession to choose so that in the future it will be in demand. Many are unsure of their choice and do not know if they are interested in it. This is probably one of the most serious problems of schoolchildren and students. And how can you help them decide? Communication with successful people in their industry can give a positive answer to this question.

And the last problem is the lack of practical orientation of education. Modern education is designed to train and educate not just a person, but also a future

scientist. But a scientist does not need all the subjects that are taught at school. He has enough of the subject with which he deals. If he needs information that is not related to his line of business, he can easily turn to any source, for example, the Internet and get the information he needs.

This is where the question comes from. What needs to be done so that the school gives not only theoretical knowledge, but also develops the personality? I think that textbooks should consider not only theoretical problems, but also practical ones that one may encounter in life. Nowadays, the education system is aimed at innovative development, so the ways to solve all these problems are aimed at moving towards the eternal new. This is not enough. We need to look objectively at the present day and at the problems in society. The fulfillment of such great tasks can only be accomplished through joint decisions and actions. It is necessary to introduce new technologies at all levels of education and provide all the necessary material, technical, scientific, methodological and information base.

There are many problems, but all of them, in my opinion, can be solved.

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